

Enhanced Efficiency Fertilizers and Climate Outcomes: Literature Review

Technical Advisory Network for Climate Smart
Agricultural Practices

June 30, 2025

ABOUT THE TECHNICAL ADVISORY NETWORK FOR CLIMATE SMART AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES

The Network emerged from a project of the [Meridian Institute](#) to better align Natural Resource Conservation Service (NRCS) Conservation Practice Standards with the best available science on GHG mitigation. In May 2024, Meridian Institute assembled six technical work groups (TWGs) to provide up-to-date scientific analysis of the impact of conservation practice adoption on GHG emissions and make technical recommendations regarding how best to achieve climate mitigation through those practices. The TWGs were comprised of academic scientists who are well regarded in their chosen field as well as scientists working within nongovernmental organizations focused on one or more of the chosen categories of interest: nutrient management, manure management, enteric methane, soil carbon, agroforestry, and grazing lands.

The technical work groups first identified agricultural practices in the six areas of interest for which evidence indicates considerable potential to reduce GHG emissions based on raw mitigation potential and adoption considerations. In August 2024 Meridian entered into a Contribution Agreement with NRCS to conduct literature reviews of the GHG emissions impacts of 39 practices, individually and in commonly practiced combinations. Meridian staff and TWG chairs and members worked with the NRCS National Discipline Leads to scope the reports and refine technical guidance regarding how best to implement practices to achieve GHG mitigation. The TWGs then conducted literature reviews, first and second-order meta-analyses, and modeling scenarios to identify the circumstances in which there is strong scientific evidence that the agricultural practices identified are likely to have net GHG benefits as well as implementation guidance for maximizing those benefits. The TWGs generated more than a dozen reports, which were delivered to NRCS in June 2025.

With the closing of Meridian Institute in mid-2025, the six technical working groups assembled by Meridian decided to establish the Network to provide a platform for sharing the work undertaken with a diversity of interested stakeholders and to support future collaboration within and/or across technical working groups. Slightly modified versions of the reports delivered to NRCS, such as this report, have been issued publicly by the Network and findings from several groups will be published in academic journals. The Network may also create briefs to summarize findings and technical recommendations for field conservationists and other interested stakeholders.

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Citation:

Brouder, Sylvie, Mike Badzmierowski, Matt Ruark, Monica Schauer, Justin Baker, Michael Castellano, Heather Darby, Mark Jacobs, and Gabriel Lobet. 2025. "Nutrient Management via Biostimulants and Climate Outcomes: Literature Review and Technical Guidance." doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15776580.

DOI: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15776580

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Executive Summary

Enhanced efficiency fertilizers (EEFs) are promoted as tools to reduce nitrogen (N) losses in crop production while maintaining yields, with the potential to provide both direct and indirect sources of N₂O emissions reduction. This umbrella review synthesizes existing systematic reviews and meta-analyses to assess the effectiveness of EEFs in reducing reactive nitrogen losses and effects on yield in temperate corn systems, especially those relevant to the U.S. Midwest.

KEY HIGHLIGHTS

- Reviews seem to be aligned that EEF products, particularly nitrification inhibitors (NIs), can reduce nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions though effects vary across studies.
- Corn yield effects are modest to negligible, typically under 2%, suggesting limited potential for productivity gains alone to justify EEF adoption. If yield gains are not consistent then it is possible the N is being lost through some unmeasured pathway in the given study or outside of the temporal scope of the study.
- Few studies test EEFs at reduced N rates, a key feature of their proposed efficiency benefit, limiting confidence in claims that EEFs enable lower fertilizer inputs without yield penalties.
- Evidence for other N loss pathways, including ammonia volatilization and nitrate leaching, is more limited and variable across reviews.
- Meta-analytical reviews often lack methodological transparency, and most do not assess the validity or bias of the underlying studies, or the variability in performance across management systems and environments.
- Results in global meta-analyses typically include a disproportionate number of studies from outside the U.S.; the dearth of U.S. EEF studies despite decades of EEF product availability reflect a long history of insufficient funding for comprehensive field studies and a publication culture that prioritizes novel and highly significant results.
- Systematic review can and should be the foundation of agriculture decision making and there is a need and an opportunity to create protocol guidelines for agricultural scientists.

BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT

Improving nitrogen use efficiency is central to reducing greenhouse gas emissions and protecting water quality in the Midwest U.S. Corn Belt. While reducing N application rates can lower emissions, it often risks yield and economic losses. EEFs are intended to mitigate this tradeoff by stabilizing nitrogen in the soil, minimizing losses through leaching, volatilization, and emissions. This review compiles evidence from existing quantitative syntheses self-described as meta-analyses to evaluate the efficacy of EEFs in U.S. Midwest corn systems or similar and identify gaps and uncertainties in the evidence base.

METHODOLOGY

This umbrella review followed the Collaboration for Environmental Evidence and ROSES reporting standards. A comprehensive search of indexed databases and grey literature was conducted to identify quantitative syntheses self-described as meta-analyses that quantified the impact of synthetic EEFs on key nitrogen loss pathways and corn productivity outcomes. After screening 614 studies identified via initial searches, only 26 met inclusion criteria. Thirteen additional studies are currently under further review for relevance. A full list of included studies will be provided in a future peer-reviewed publication. Eligibility criteria excluded reviews focused solely on modeling, non-field data, or studies without a control treatment of a conventional, non-EEF N fertilizer. Studies excluded at the full-text level will be provided with rationale for their exclusion upon peer-reviewed publication.

FINDINGS

Initial findings suggest:

- EEF types vary in effectiveness, with NIs showing the most consistent N₂O reductions.
- Ammonia volatilization and nitrate loss data are less robust.
- Reviews rarely disaggregate results by both fertilizer EEF type and/or application rate.
- Yield benefits are generally minor to negligible, casting doubt on the economic case for EEFs in the absence of regulatory or incentive structures and their true effectiveness of reducing total N loss
- Most analyses had the majority of studies from non-U.S. settings and may lack applicability to Midwest conditions; management and environmental details were often inadequate to characterize efficacy for U.S. conditions.
- The common design of comparing EEFs to conventional fertilizer at the same N rate fails to test whether EEFs improve nitrogen efficiency sufficiently to justify N rate reductions.

CONCLUSION

While early evidence supports EEFs for reducing nitrous oxide emissions, current reviews offer limited support for consistent yield or full nitrogen efficiency improvements, particularly under reduced N scenarios. Gaps in study design and lack of rate-stratified analysis constrain our ability to draw strong conclusions. Caution is advised in using current meta-analyses to guide policy or farmer decision-making without additional quality screening and regional analysis. We recommend that the USDA require rigorous systematic reviews of specific questions and outcomes for their Conservation Practice Standards prior to the inclusion of various management strategies like EEFs for better nutrient management.

Background

Enhanced-efficiency fertilizers (EEFs) are a category of nitrogen (N) fertilizers specifically designed to improve nitrogen use efficiency (NUE) by synchronizing nitrogen release with crop uptake more effectively. These fertilizers aim to reduce N losses to the environment, such as nitrate (NO_3^-) leaching, ammonia (NH_3) volatilization, and nitrous oxide (N_2O) emissions, while maintaining or improving crop yields. EEFs include controlled-release fertilizers that regulate nutrient release over time, as well as nitrogen stabilizers such as urease inhibitors (which slow the hydrolysis of urea) and nitrification inhibitors (which delay the microbial conversion of ammonium to nitrate). When combined, these stabilizers are referred to as "double inhibitors" and can simultaneously reduce multiple N loss pathways. By targeting critical windows of nitrogen vulnerability in the soil-plant system, EEFs offer a promising strategy for reducing reactive nitrogen losses without compromising agricultural productivity.

EEF importance becomes especially clear in the context of rising environmental pressures and the economic tradeoffs involved in reducing nitrogen application rates. While lowering N inputs reduces emissions, it often comes with yield penalties such that emissions per unit area are lower but emissions per unit production are higher. For example, Zhao et al. (2017) found that reducing N rates by 25% could improve fertilizer recovery by 30% and reduce N_2O emissions by a similar margin but also warned of yield and economic losses. Similarly, Baum et al. (2025) used simulations to demonstrate that reducing N below economically optimal levels could result in yield declines of 3–14%, depending on the crop and the assumptions used. These findings highlight a critical role for EEFs, provided they are effective in enabling environmental gains without undermining farm profitability and yield.

Interest in the application of meta-analytical statistics to agricultural questions has increased exponentially in the past two decades. When completed with strict adherence to formal protocols for a systematic review (SR), these quantitative syntheses can identify direction, magnitude, and certainty of an agricultural management intervention when compared to a control or "business as usual" approach to on-farm technology implementation. Umbrella reviews compile evidence from multiple systematic reviews into a single, accessible, and usable document, focusing on a broad condition or problem for which there are two or more potential interventions (Grant and Booth, 2009). The purpose is to highlight relevant, high-quality reviews that address these potential interventions and their results, to describe what is known to inform recommendations for practice, and to identify critical knowledge gaps that should be prioritized in new research. Existing systematic reviews with meta-analyses can themselves be quantitatively synthesized, offering a fast-track approach to informing policy decisions. When time and resources are limited, Makowski et al. (2023) demonstrated that second-order meta-analytical (SOMA) methodologies exist that can deliver results similar to a reanalysis of the primary literature, provided existing first-order meta-analyses are of high quality and minimally redundant.

This umbrella review aims to synthesize and evaluate existing systematic reviews and meta-analyses on the agronomic and environmental performance of EEFs in temperate corn (maize) systems, specifically those applicable to the U.S. Midwest. Specifically, this study aims to employ a systematic approach to identifying relevant syntheses that have used meta-analysis statistics to assess the effects of EEFs on any of the key nitrogen loss pathways, including nitrate leaching, ammonia volatilization, nitrous oxide emissions, or soil nitrate and ammonium concentration status, or corn grain yield. The goal is to identify consistent patterns, assess tradeoffs or co-benefits, and evaluate the strength and generalizability of the first-order meta-analysis evidence to inform nitrogen management strategies and policy in temperate

corn cropping systems in the U.S. The final findings are intended to be published in the second half of 2025, including a full qualitative analysis of the methods used in each included synthesis for this report.

Methodology

Our research question was: Do N transformation EEFs (i.e., inhibitors and slow-release technologies) reduce direct and indirect emissions of nitrous oxide and improve field-scale N balances in Midwest US corn production? We intend only to look at synthetic EEFs applied in conjunction with synthetic fertilizers for the purpose of this study.

Table 1. Summary elements of the primary question include population, intervention, comparator, outcome, and study type	
Population	Corn grown primarily with inorganic N fertilizer in temperate regions, similar to the U.S. Midwest
Intervention	Chemicals or coatings designed to slow biological or enzymatic transformations of N fertilizers in soil
Comparator	Corn production with synthetic fertilizer rates without fertilizer technology enhancement (ideally would include suboptimal rate controls)
Outcome(s)	Field scale indicators of N balance, N ₂ O emissions, NH ₃ volatilization, NO ₃ -N leaching, soil NH ₄ ⁺ and NO ₃ ⁻ concentrations, efficiency of fertilizer use, corn yield
Study Type	Studies self-described as systematic reviews or similar rigorous research syntheses and/or meta-analyses

This review conforms to the Collaboration of Environmental Evidence (CEE) Evidence Guidelines and Standards for Evidence Synthesis and to the RepOrting Standards for Systematic Evidence Synthesis (ROSES) for systematic review (Haddaway et al., 2017).

SEARCH STRATEGY

A comprehensive search was conducted to identify relevant reviews, primarily from peer-reviewed literature. As systematic reviews and meta-analyses have increased rapidly in recent years, a search of dissertations and theses was also conducted to retrieve any recent syntheses that have not yet been published in the peer-reviewed literature. Table 2 summarizes key search criteria that informed our initial scan of the literature.

KEYWORD AND SEARCH STRING DEVELOPMENT

SEARCHING THE LITERATURE

Table 2. List of the indexing platforms and the web-based search engine in which the search strategy was deployed.					
Source Type	Source Name	Indexes	Subscription	Limits, Restrictions, Filters	Platform Provider
Indexing Platforms	Web of Science Core collection	SCI-Expanded 1900 – pres.; CPCI-S 1990 – pres.; BKCI-S 2005 – pres.; ESCI 2005 – pres.; CCR-Expanded 1985 – pres.; IC 1993 – pres.	Purdue Univ.	Topic (TS) search	Clarivate
	CABI	CAB Abstracts 1973 – pres.; Global Health 1912 – pres.	Purdue Univ.	Topic (TS) search	Clarivate
	ProQuest™		Purdue Univ.	Topic (TS) search	Clarivate
	Scopus		Purdue Univ.	Title Abstract Keyword (TITLE-ABS-KEY) search of documents	Elsevier
	AGRICOLA		Purdue Univ. Ovid Interface	All field (.af) search	National Agricultural Library
Web-based search engine	Google Scholar	Google Scholar	NA		

As an example, our final Scopus search string was: (TITLE-ABS-KEY (corn OR maize OR "Zea mays")) AND ((TITLE-ABS-KEY (inhibit* OR stabil* OR "controlled release" OR "enhanced efficiency" OR eef* OR "polymer coated" OR (mitigat* W/3 (practice* OR management* OR strateg*)))) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY ((nitrogen OR n) AND (fertili* OR amend*) AND (rate OR quantit* OR amount* OR applic* OR management* OR practice*)))) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY (n2o OR "nitrous oxide" OR "greenhouse gas" OR ghg OR "N los*" OR "nitrogen los*" OR ((nh3 OR ammonia) near/3 AND volitali*) OR ((nitrate OR no3) W/3 leach*) OR ((use OR utili* OR uptake OR agronomic OR recovery) near/5 AND efficien*)))

For all other search strings and the development of each string, please see the included Excel file "search_string_strategy_EEFs."

ARTICLE SCREENING AND STUDY ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

SCREENING PROCESS

Screening and reference management was conducted using Covidence (2025), a web-based collaboration software platform that streamlines the production of systematic and other literature reviews. Two reviewers were required for screening titles and abstracts for relevance (Screen 1) and required for full text screening in keeping with eligibility criteria. A total of 614 references were found across all databases, Covidence identified 290 duplicates with another 34 duplicates identified and removed manually. Title and abstract screening of the 290 unique references identified 171 irrelevant references leaving 119 references to be screened against inclusion / exclusion criteria. In our double-blind review process for inclusion in this study, we agreed on excluding 74 publications because these were (i) neither meta-analyses nor systematic reviews (18), (ii) not explorations of impacts of EEFs but focused on other aspects of 4R technology (16), and/or (iii) or not otherwise fit to the purpose of our question (e.g., not representative of Midwest US corn production systems) (40). In the case of studies that did not fit our purpose, common reasons included averaging in results for corn with all other arable crops or not having a no-EFF control at a similar N rate. We agreed to include 26 studies and an additional 13 studies require more analysis to reach agreement on their relevance.

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

Table 3 highlights the inclusion and exclusion criteria used for screening the literature.

Criteria	Overview	Included	Excluded
Population/subject of interest	Field corn grown in the US Midwest using fertilizer N from predominantly inorganic sources	Any rotation (E.g. continuous corn, corn soybean rotations, corn-wheat, double crop soybean, etc.); geographic regions outside the U.S. Midwest under similar management intensities in temperate environments	Popcorn, sweet corn, field corn grown with manure or other organic N amendments (e.g. biosolids), in agroecozones not represented in the U.S. Midwest; subsistence or smallholder production environments
Intervention	Existing commercial EEF technologies for N cycle modification	Urease inhibitors, nitrification inhibitors, controlled release (e.g. sulfur or polymer coated products)	Biochar, biostimulants, nano fertilizers, novel EEF not yet commercially available or in very limited use (e.g. sensor or plant signal molecules)
Comparator	Inorganically fertilized maize without EEF technology	Similar fertilization approach to intervention minus the EEF technology	Comparisons among EEFs without a “no EEF” control

Outcome	System N balance	Measures of direct and indirect N loss (N ₂ O emission, NH ₃ volatilization, NO ₃ leaching), other measures of field scale N balances (e.g. yield, agronomic or N use efficiency studies)	Modeling / simulated outcomes; system component reviews (e.g. soil or microbial community only).
Study Type	Systematic or systematized reviews and / or meta-analyses	Any study that self-describes with an array of terms as more rigorous than a standard, narrative review or use the term meta-analysis in the title or abstract	Narrative reviews that provide no indication of how primary literature was selected. Opinion or editorial style perspectives. Modeling studies

STUDY VALIDITY ASSESSMENT

While not a current component of this report, the final peer-reviewed published article will include a study validity assessment of each included synthesis where we assess the transparency, methodology, and rigor of each review. This will allow us to have an improved understanding of which syntheses may hold higher merit and validity to answer our central question on the effects of EEFs in temperate corn systems on N loss, N use efficiency, and corn yield. Due to this being a time-intensive component of a good systematic review, this could not be completed for inclusion in this report. Of particular concern is the lack of transparency in the primary studies included in a meta-analysis and the extent to which studies may be duplicative and represent contemporaneous analyses of the same bodies of primary literature. A full bibliometric analysis is required to understand which publications are novel and which are largely redundant. Reasons studies were considered less relevant include restricted study geographies (e.g. China only: Xia2017) and a focus on a specific experimental technique without assessing any N loss pathways (e.g. N=15 studies of yield and N uptake only, Quan2021) (Table 4).

Current Findings

It is important to note that the findings presented here represent what has been currently extracted from a set of the syntheses included. The findings for this report do not yet incorporate all included syntheses nor the most critical evaluative step: a formal assessment of study validity or methodological quality for each included review. The reliability of the reported effects is ultimately dependent on the quality of the underlying primary studies, yet none of the reviews summarized here conducted a comprehensive risk of bias or validity assessment of the primary studies they included. Further, most meta-analyses present results as ratios or percentage change. While percent change is important, a full understanding of impact requires characterization of absolute magnitude of effect, which may be uncoverable within the written text and/or within supplementary material. As a result, while these aggregate findings are informative, they should be interpreted with caution until additional quality appraisal is completed.

SCOPE AND COVERAGE OF SYNTHESSES

The included syntheses (Table 4) span global to regional scales and assess a wide range of EEFs, including nitrification inhibitors (NI), urease inhibitors (UI), controlled-release fertilizers (CRF), and dual inhibitors (DI). While all reviews include corn, many also cover other staple and specialty crops such as wheat, rice, vegetables, and forage grasses. Nitrogen application rates varied across studies, with some offering detailed rate-stratified results (e.g., Lu et al. 2023), while others left rates unspecified. Reviews such as Decock (2014), Eagle et al. (2017), Abalos et al. (2016), and Sully et al. (2019) are highly relevant to U.S. corn systems, particularly in the Midwest.

NITROGEN LOSS PATHWAYS ASSESSED

The primary N loss pathways examined include nitrous oxide (N_2O) emissions, NH_3 volatilization, and NO_3^- leaching and runoff. Some reviews also evaluated nitric oxide (NO) emissions and changes in soil nitrogen pools (NH_4^+ and NO_3^-). Several studies, particularly those from Xia et al. (2017), Guo et al. (2023), Tufail et al. (2023), Lu et al. (2023), and Zhang et al. (2024) provided quantitative comparisons of EEF types across multiple of these loss pathways.

PRODUCTIVITY OUTCOMES

Yield (YD), nitrogen uptake (NU), and nitrogen use efficiency (NUE) were common agronomic outcomes reported. EEFs showed minimal to no yield effect in corn systems (Table 5). For example, Sully (2019) reported a mean effect range of +0.7 to 1.4% increase in corn yield in the Midwest U.S. with NIs. Nitrogen use efficiency improvements were observed by Xia et al. (2017) (geographical scope only China) with NIs and CRFs. However, a global analysis by Quan et al. (2021) found no significant effect when pooling across EEF types and N rates.

EFFECTIVENESS BY EEF TYPE

Most existing reviews report impacts of EEF products as a percent change from that reported for a control (commonly identical rate of a non-EEF N source) and report a weighted mean of the included studies and its 95% confidence interval. In statistical meta-analysis individual studies contributing to a mean are weighted by their precision. Meta-analysis results show NIs reduced N_2O emissions, with mean effects ranging from -27% to -51% depending on the study (Table 5). CRFs also reduced N_2O emissions significantly (e.g., Lu et al. 2023: -15.4%; Xia et al. 2017: -25.2%). NH_3 volatilization showed greater variability. For CRFs, reductions ranged from -32% to -59%, while NIs effects were suggested to have no effect. See Table 5 for a detailed breakdown of findings from extracted syntheses.

LIMITATIONS AND GAPS

Despite the initial strong findings for EEFs for this report, there are several notable limitations and gaps. Some syntheses lacked disaggregation of results by fertilizer rate and/or type, and others included non-field studies (e.g., incubation or pot trials). NH_3 and NO_3^- effects were underrepresented relative to N_2O , and few reviews reported results stratified by both EEF type and N rate. Additionally, many globally scoped reviews contained few U.S.-based studies, reducing their direct applicability to North American systems. Potentially the most important and most limiting with respect to our question was the common design of the studies to compare EEFs with the control at the same N application rate. While useful, this does not address one of the key claims of EEFs: if they work at improving nitrogen use efficiency, then a reduction of N fertilizer rate should be possible. However, most primary studies do not test this “sub-optimal” N application rate (i.e. most showed no response in yield). Lyons et al. (2025)

highlight the need to conduct trials that test a zero N applied control, “sub-optimal”, “optimal”, and “excessive” N rates with and without the EEF technology to see how the products work at varying rates both for N loss pathways and crop yield. Otherwise, as Rose et al. (2018) points out, we should expect increased yield gains consistently. If yield gains are not consistent then it is possible the N is being lost through some unmeasured pathway in the given study or outside of the temporal scope of the study. Almost a decade ago, Eagle et al. (2017) remarked that U.S. corn system studies of fertilizer technology impacts on N₂O emissions and NO₃ leaching were conducted in separate geographies (Colorado vs U.S. Midwest). These geographies correspond to corn producing regions with vast differences in soil drainage and artificial drainage enhancements; when present, artificial drainage can dramatically alter the predominant N loss pathways and both regions and N loss pathways need to be represented in a review to capture the inference space for EEF effectiveness across the US Cornbelt. Due to the lack of inclusion of primary studies assessing the varying levels of N application rates with and without EEFs we and others like Rose et al. (2018) urge caution when interpreting these syntheses.

Finally, we note that although products labelled as EEFs have been commercially available for decades, insufficient funding and previously limited scientific interest in product testing are major contributing factors to the paucity of U.S. studies in the peer-review literature and therefore their inclusion in the existing meta-analyses. Historically, federal agencies had little interest in supporting field trials to demonstrate yield and efficiency benefits of novel fertilizer products. Funding for this research was primarily from the fertilizer industry, commodity groups, and/or fertilizer check-off programs and monies were generally inadequate for rigorous research. For example, when the controlled release product ESN became available in 2004, Agrium, the manufacturer, wanted University Extension Specialists to run replicated field trails with multiple N rate comparisons of ESN to various non-EEF N sources but offered almost no support for an experimental design requiring multiple soil and plant measurements. Purdue University in Indiana received \$5000 for a 1-yr, 4 replicate, 2 product, 5 N rate study measuring yield, and plant N status and soil profile N leaching throughout the growing season. In this study, the impact of ESN was not significant, the study was not repeated, and the data remain unpublished because peer review journals typically require multiple years of data and prefer novel versus confirmatory studies and significant versus non-significant results. This “file-drawer” and publication bias problem in soil fertility research is now widely recognized motivating data stewardship initiatives to facilitate meta-analysis (Fixen et al. 2016) as included in the recently published EEF research protocols (Lyons et al., 2025).

Tables 4 and 5 include a range of abbreviations used to summarize fertilizer types, nitrogen compounds, performance metrics, and study details. Fertilizer types include NI (nitrification inhibitor), UI (urease inhibitor), CRF (controlled-release fertilizer), and DI (dual inhibitor). Common N loss and soil N forms and compounds include N₂O (nitrous oxide), NH₃ (ammonia), NH₄⁺ (ammonium), NO₃⁻ (nitrate), NO (nitric oxide), and Nr (reactive nitrogen). Agronomic performance metrics are abbreviated as YD (yield), NU (nitrogen uptake), and NUE (nitrogen use efficiency). Fertilizer formulations and inhibitors include DCD (dicyandiamide), DMPP (3,4-dimethylpyrazole phosphate), DNPP (dinitrophenol derivative), NBPT (N-(n-butyl) thiophosphoric triamide), HQ (hydroquinone), BNI (biological nitrification inhibition), and PCU (polymer-coated urea). Nitrogen fertilizer sources include UAN (urea ammonium nitrate), AA (anhydrous ammonia), AS (ammonium sulfate), and AqA (aqua ammonia). Additional abbreviations include kg N ha⁻¹ (kilograms of nitrogen per hectare), Ave ± SD (average plus or minus standard deviation), and NA (not available or not applicable).

Study	Population	Scale	EFFs	Chem	rate(s) Kg N ha	Source	Nr Path	Crop Prod.	Soil	Relev.	Notes
Decock 2014	Corn	USA	DI, CRF	DCD+NBPT, Poly-coated	100 – 210	Not Sp., urea	N2O			High	No impacts on yields
Xia 2017	Corn, wheat, rice	China	NI, UI, CRF	DCD/DMPP/ nitrapyrin, HQ/NBPT, S- or poly-coated	>200, 200 – 300, > 300		N2O, NH3, NO3	YD, NU, NUE		Med.-H	N rate(s) not explicit for EFF comparison; not U.S. but considers multiple impacts
Ti 2019	Corn, rice, wheat, veg., pasture	Global	NI, UI, CRF	Not spec.	Not spec.	Not spec.	NH3			Med.-H	NH3 focus is not well-represented in the lit.
Tufail 2022	Corn, rice, wheat, veg., other crops, grasses, fallow	Global	NI	DCD, DNPP	Not spec.	Not Spec.	NH3, N2O, NO, NO3	YD, NU, NUE	NH4, NO3	Med	Same data as Tufail 2023 w/ exception that this paper includes NH3 data for corn

Thapa 2016	Corn, wheat, rice	Global	NI, UI, DI, CR F	All (see Table 2)	Not spec.	Not spec.	N2O	YD		Med-H	US Cornbelt studies included. US centric; UI for corn not shown
Lu 2023	Corn, wheat, rice	Global	CR F	Not specified	<100, 100 – 200, > 200	Urea	N2O, NH3			M-H	Maize and N rate data shown separately. N rate no impact on effects
Hu 2014	Rapeseed, potato, barley, corn	Germany	NI		Not specified	Not spec.		YD		Med.	Corn data limited (silage only)
Tufail 2023	Corn, rice, wheat, veg., other crops, grasses, fallow	Global	NI	DCD, DNPP	Not spec.	Not Spec.	NH3, N2O, NO, NO3	YD, NU, NUE	NH4, NO3	High	28 countries incl. U.S.; # of maize studies not spec. in main article; values may incl. pot & incub. Studies
Zhang 2024	Corn, rice, wheat, soybean, rape	Global	CR F	Not specified	50 – 600	Not spec.	NH3, N2O, NO, NO3	YD, NU, NUE		High	Runoff and leaching may include NH4+; corn results agg. over N rate & no rate specific info.
Eagle 2017	Corn	USA & Canada	DI, CR F	DCD+NB PT, poly-coated		UAN / Urea, urea	N2O			High	NO3 not assessed for EEFs
Abalos 2016	Corn	USA & Canada	CR F	DCD+NB PT/ Nitrapyrin, poly-coated	165±51 (Ave±SD)	Various, urea	N2O	YD		High	N rate is “normal” for region

Wolt 2004	Corn, wheat (1 sorghum study)	USA (includes 1 German study)	NI	Nitrapyrin	45 – 431	All forms	N ₂ O (predominant GHG cont.), NO ₃ (presumed)	YD	NO ₃ -+NH ₄ +	M-H	No MA stats (i.e. not weighted); lit rev. not a SR; all crops comb.
Quan 2021	Corn	Global	EEFs combined	Not described	181±38 (Ave±SD)	Urea, NH ₄ -based		YD, NU		M-H	Only N15 studies, reducing N rate reduced YD, NU
Guo 2023	Corn, fruit, vegetable, grass, oilseed rape, wheat, and rice	Global (only 1 USA study)	NI, UI	Various (DMPP, DCD, Nitrapyrin, BNI, NBPT, NI+UI)	Not specified	Not specified	NH ₃ , N ₂ O (both yield-scaled and not)	YD	NO ₃ -, NH ₄ +	Med	Only includes 1 study from USA, heavily skewed towards Chinese studies
Sully 2019 (Ch. 2)	Corn	Mid western, USA	NI	Nitrapyrin, DCD/NBP T+DCD (but they judged the distributions to be independent and combined all data)	60-280	Various (does not subgroup by fertilizer type, but contains urea, UAN, AA, AS, AqA)	none	YD		High	Regionally specific however, only assess impacts of NIs on corn grain yield

Table 5. Findings from included reviews based on EEF type on N loss pathway or corn yield						
Intervention	Impact	Direction	Mean Effect (%)	95% CI	# of studies (pairs)†	Ref. ID (additional note)
NI	N ₂ O	Decrease	-38.3	-48.0: -28.9	NA (34)	Xia2017 (N ₂ O emis.; Fig. 4b)
		Decrease	-51.1	-61.4: -41.7	NA (31)	Thapa2016 (Corn; Fig2a)
	NH ₃	No Effect	+21.0	-9.5: +55.6	NA (5)	Xia2017 (NH ₃ emis.; Fig. 4b)
		No effect	+5.5	-100.0: +54.0	NA (12 or 5; fig. error)	Ti2019 (NI Maize; Fig. 2)
	YD	Increase	+6.8	+4.5: +9.3	NA (48)	Xia2017 (Grain yld.; Fig. 1b)
		No effect	+2.7	-6.9: +8.5	NA (8)	Thapa2016 (Corn; Fig2a)
		Increase	+0.7-1.4	[+0.1-1.8] (study used multiple statistical approaches and this is represented in the rage)	Variance weighted analysis = 185, Bootstrapping (with replication weighting) and unweighted	Sully2019 (Corn; Table 3)

					analysis = 266	
	NU	Increase	+10.5	+4.9: +16.4	NA (11)	Xia2017 (Tot. N up.; Fig. 1b)
UI	NH3	No Effect	-44.9	-83.2: +0.3	NA (5)	Xia2017 (NH3 emis.; Fig. 4c)
		Decrease	-36.0	-54.2: -9.8	NA 21	Ti2019 (UI Maize, Fig. 2)
	NO3	Decrease	-36.1	-49.0: -23.7	NA (6)	Xia2017 (Grain yld.; Fig. 4c)
	YD	Increase	+6.1	+3.8: +8.7	NA (32)	Xia2017 (Grain yld.; Fig. 1c)
DI	N2O	Decrease	-27.4	-43.8: -6.5	NA (20)	Abalos2016 (w/:w/out inhib; Fig.1)
		No Effect	-17.2	-38.9: +4.6	2 (9)	Eagle2017 (UAN+Agro. ISO UAN; yield scaled; Fig.3)
		Decrease	-26.8	-35.9: -15.3	10 (64)	Decock2014 (no inhib, vs DCD- NBPT; Fig. 3)¥
		Decrease	-29.3	-37.3: -21.2	NA (58)	Thapa2016 (Corn; Fig4a)
	YD	No Effect	+1.0	-1.4: +3.5	NA (39)	Abalos2016 (w/out:w/ inhib; Fig.2)
		Increase	+1.5	+0.1: +3.1	NA (42)	Thapa2016 (Corn; Fig.4b)
	NU					
CRF	N2O	Decrease	-15.4	-21.1: -9.8	NA (102)	LU 2023 (Maize, Fig. 4b)

		No effect	-5.3	-17.9: +7.2	6 (46)	Eagle2017 (Coated Urea ISO Urea; yield scaled; Fig. 3)
		Decrease	-25.8	-38.8: -13.2	4 (25)	Eagle2017 (SuperU ISO urea; yield scaled; Fig.3)
		Decrease	-17.6	-31.3: -4.0	2 (10)	Eagle2017 (SuperU ISOUAN; yield scaled; Fig.3)
		No effect	-8.8	-22.1: +7.6	NA (40)	Abalos2016 (U vs PCU; Fig.1)
		No Effect	-3.8	-16.6: +12.0	5 (40)	Decock2014 (U vs PCU; Fig.3)‡
		Decrease	-25.2	-36.3: -13.5	NA (32)	Xia2017 (N ₂ O emis.; Fig. 4 ^a)
		Decrease	-17.6	-26.3: -8.0	NA (83)	Thapa2016 (Corn; Fig. 5a)
	NH ₃	Decrease	-32.0	-40.0: -24.5	NA (102)	LU2023 (Maize, Fig. 2b)
		Decrease	-59.1	-69.5: -48.0	NA (18)	Xia2017 (NH ₃ emis.; Fig. 4a)
		Decrease	-43.1	-60.9: -16.4	NA (5 or 17; fig. error)	Ti2019 (CRF Maize; Fig. 2)
	NO ₃	Decrease	-28.3	-47.4: -4.3	NA (4)	Xia2017 (N leach.; Fig. 4a)‡
		Decrease	-22.2	-28.3: -16.0	NA (16)	Xia2017 (N runoff.; Fig. 4a)
	YD	No Effect	-0.2	-7.8: +7.9	NA (26)	Abalos2016 (U vs PCU; Fig.2)
		Increase	+6.7	+4.5: +8.5	NA (119)	Xia2017 (Grain yld.; Fig. 1a)

		No Effect	-0.9	-5.2: +3.3	NA (60)	Thapa2016 (Corn; Fig. 5b)
	NU	Increase	+11.2	+8.2: +14.3	NA (59)	Xia2017 (Tot. N up.; Fig. 1a)
EEF not sp.	YD	No effect	-1.55	-4.66: +1.94	15 (28)	Quan 2021 (EEFs; Fig. 2a)
	NU	No effect	-0.49	-3.20: +5.12	13 (24)	Quan 2021 (EEFs, Fig. 2b)
<p>† Number of sites or number of studies from which pairs of observations were extracted; often neither were reported (NA).</p> <p>‡ Xia et al. report both N leaching and N runoff but N speciation not specified and likely includes NH₄⁺</p> <p>¥ Decock estimates the effect as increase without the EEF; results presented back-calculating the effect as a decrease with use of an EEF.</p>						

Conclusion

While we urge caution based on our synthesis still in progress and the limitations and gaps we identified so far in the work and area of research, initial evidence suggests EEFs compared to same synthetic nitrogen rate with no EEF technology offer limited to no yield gains for U.S. Midwest corn systems. However, our initial findings also suggest there is evidence that EEFs may reduce yield-scaled reactive nitrogen losses (especially N₂O). The magnitude and consistency of these effects vary by product type, study design, and environmental context. Further regionally specific and rate-stratified (relative to agronomic optimum N rates) meta-analyses would improve decision-making for nitrogen management in U.S. Midwest corn systems.

Moving Forward

NEXT STEPS

To develop this preliminary report into a peer-review quality publication, we will proceed as follows:

1. Complete a preliminary inclusion/exclusion assessment of the final 13 papers and fully develop and apply quality and relevance (validity) frameworks for classifying the meta-evaluations in our study. Details for these assessments are as follows:
2. External validity (relevance) evaluation: This concerns the specific relevance of an existing meta-analysis to our question including whether existing meta-analytical corn results are specific to the climatic regions and soils of the Cornbelt as well as whether other 4R practices are relevant to farmer practice in the U.S. (Note: we have already developed and piloted this evaluation framework),
3. Quality and internal validity (bias) evaluation: This evaluation focuses on assessment for systematic (vs random) errors in the existing reviews. We will evaluate papers and rank on the transparency and repeatability of the searches used to identify the papers included in the meta-analysis, the inclusions and exclusion criteria, and whether extracted databases are available for reanalysis and updating. We will also evaluate and rank papers on their statistical approaches as preliminary review suggests many did not appropriately weight studies when synthesizing EEFs effect sizes. Failure to correctly weight studies in meta-analysis is known to contribute to the overestimation of effect sizes (i.e. magnitude and certainty of EEF impact). We will also look for evidence that publication bias (also known as the “file drawer” problem) has been considered in the review and, if so, how.
4. Conduct a bibliometric analysis of all included reviews and meta-analyses using Bibliometrix (<https://www.bibliometrix.org/home/index.php>). This analysis will allow us to rapidly confirm redundant and largely duplicative publications, as well as identify the influential author groups and collaborations. Identify the degree of overlap is the first step in understanding whether a second order meta-analysis of existing meta-analyses will contribute to our understanding of EEF impacts (magnitude and certainty) or artificially inflate certainty around outcomes of EEF implementation at scale.
5. Complete the extraction of effect measures for all papers that are deemed to be of medium and higher relevance to our question (i.e. complete and finalize the content of Table 5).

6. Complete a second order meta-analysis of relevant and non-redundant existing meta-analyses if warranted.
7. Based on our findings, draft manuscript that:
8. Characterizes the direction (large (>15%), ... zero, ambiguous/bidirectional, increase) and confidence in direction of EEF impacts. For confidence in direction, we will use a modification of existing IPCC frameworks (Mach et al., 2017; Kause et al., 2022) to characterize specific EEF products and associated N management strategies into an existing evidence (low to high) and expert opinion (low to high agreement among experts) matrix to inform farmers and policy.
9. Map critical gaps relevant to our question “Do N transformation EEFs (i.e., inhibitors and slow-release technologies) reduce direct and indirect emissions of nitrous oxide and improve field-scale N balances in Midwest US corn production?”, and
10. Identifies common problems with existing systematic reviews and meta-analysis that result in low quality analyses that are generally not fit to any particular purpose.

FUTURE CONSIDERATIONS FOR EVIDENCE-BASED PRACTICE

Systematic review and appropriate application of meta-analytical statistics are the gold standard for converting scientific results into guidelines, policies and recommendations for evidence-based practice. Widely used in medicine to help people make informed health decisions (<https://www.cochrane.org/>), the methodology is now used in numerous other fields to set policy and practice guidelines. A decade ago, the Environmental Protection Agency collaborated with the National Research Council to revise its Integrated Risk Information System and apply a rigorous systematic review approach to the development of chemical toxicology values (National Research Council, 2014). As demonstrated by this report, systematic review and meta-analyses in agriculture are now rapidly increasing, a reflection of increased awareness of the potential utility and high citation rate of such syntheses and access to literature search engines and statistical software. However, most authors and journal editors lack any formal training in the methodology, and this has resulted in large numbers of publications that are of low quality and are not designed to address specific stakeholder needs. In an effort similar to our analysis of existing EEF syntheses, Krupnik et al (2019) reviewed the use of meta-analysis in the debates around organic and conservation agriculture and concluded that, for these highly politicized topics, how the meta-analyses were constructed impacted the generalizability and usefulness of the studies. More recently, Fohrafellner et al. (2023) reviewed the quality of 31 meta-analyses on management practices and soil organic carbon and found only one to be of high quality with major deficiencies impacting the utility of majority of the studies. For questions regarding the use of EEFs to simultaneously maintain farmer profitability and reduce environmental N losses, we suggest the following:

1. Entities interested in implementing policy can and should adopt systematic review and meta-analysis as the foundation for decision making, and
2. The systematic reviews to support decision making must be high quality, transparent and fit for purpose which, in turn, requires...
 - a) Stakeholder engagement in question design and review development to ensure systematic review outcomes will meet high priority needs,

- b) Training materials for agricultural scientists (researchers and editors) on the systematic review protocols and best practices, and
3. A sufficient volume of high-quality primary literature that covers the farmer practices, systems, and prevailing environmental conditions for which the guidance is supposed to apply.

We did not review the primary literature to understand its suitability for new syntheses that would more directly address the question we posed here regarding enhanced efficiency, maintained productivity and reduced direct and indirect emissions with specific EEFs and reduced N rates but anticipate gaps with respect to pathways, products and other aspects of 4R management. The Efficient Fertilizer Consortium (<https://foundationfar.org/consortia/efficient-fertilizer-consortium/>) was created to support new primary studies in this area and the Lyons et al. (2025) guidelines are designed to ensure primary studies capture the data required for subsequent creation of high-quality meta-analysis. This includes the collection of information on system attributes anticipated to be important covariates determining outcomes. There is need and opportunity to create similar protocol guidance for synthesizing the science into products useful to agencies interested in defensible practice standards in farmer support programs.

Science Gaps and Recommendations

Critical science gaps need to be filled to improve GHG mitigation research, data collection, and modeling tools to better understand the potential of conservation agriculture practices to mitigate agricultural GHG emissions within and across agricultural sectors. The gaps and needs identified below and associated recommendations are oriented to achieving the goal of enabling GHG mitigation assessment capabilities at the granularity necessary to meaningfully guide agricultural practice adoption and implementation decisions to optimize GHG mitigation across a range of geographic and operational settings. Such assessment capabilities would inform and improve the development and refinement of public and private sector practice standards, policies, programs, and investments to incentivize practices to optimize achievement of GHG mitigation alongside profitability for farmers, cost-effectiveness for incentive and cost-share programs, and achievement of other conservation objectives.

There is substantial and growing research on nutrient management strategies for increasing farm profitability, reducing nutrient losses, and supporting GHG mitigation goals. Specifically, the extent to which a 4R nitrogen management strategy (right rate, right source, right timing, and right placement) can simultaneously achieve farm profitability and environmental stewardship has been studied extensively in the context of soil fertility, water quality, and (to a lesser extent) GHG emissions. Despite these scientific advances, key knowledge and data gaps remain, limiting the potential usefulness of decision support frameworks. We outline several of these gaps below and potential steps for improving information, modeling tools, and nutrient management recommendations.

RESEARCH

- Significant data and research gaps inhibit the understanding of GHG mitigation potential through an expanding array of nutrient management practices. However, fertilizer application and associated nutrient management practices account for a significant portion of GHG emissions from agriculture,

and reduction in application rate is one of the most certain forms of GHG reductions available within agricultural systems. Therefore, a comprehensive scientific roadmap for GHG mitigation through nutrient management is crucial. This roadmap should:

- Articulate the existing research and key gaps from on the ground science and how it links, or fails to link, with modeling and farmer decision making.
 - Determine the tools, guidelines, and information needed for a company to credibly claim GHG reductions and chart a pathway to achieve this.
 - Address/understand variation rather than identify the average effect with NM products to develop probability-based metrics.
 - Develop an understanding of how, when, and where NM products are used to help define what can be considered an Enhanced Efficiency Fertilizer in practice.
 - Outline proper design of contributing experiments to build the evidence base from in-field experiments.
 - Lyons et al., 2024 does this to some extent, but this paper stops short of recommending quantitative considerations for experimental designs (power analysis, etc.) so there is more to build on.¹
 - Develop a similar guide for meta-analyses to ensure meta-data are useful for models and policy, as discussed below.
- Field research measuring the efficacy of biostimulants across representative sites and cropping systems is lacking, especially research following proper guidelines for measuring product efficacy.

DECISION SUPPORT ANALYSIS

- Entities interested in implementing policy should adopt systematic review and meta-analysis as the foundation for decision making. Systematic reviews to support decision making must be high quality, transparent and fit for purpose which, in turn, requires:
 - Stakeholder engagement in question design and review development to ensure systematic review outcomes will meet high priority needs,
 - Training materials for agricultural scientists (researchers and editors) on the systematic review protocols and best practices, and
 - A sufficient volume of high-quality primary literature that covers the farmer practices, systems, and prevailing environmental conditions for which the guidance is supposed to apply.
- Standard modeling approaches to quantify technoeconomic or market opportunity costs of nutrient management strategies offer an overly simplistic perspective of potential mitigation costs.

¹ Lyons, S. E., Arnall, D. B., Ashford-Kornburger, D., Brouder, S. M., Christian, E., Dobermann, A., ... & Wagner-Riddle, C. (2025). Field trial guidelines for evaluating enhanced efficiency fertilizers. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 89(1), e20787.

- E.g., Models often assume simple average yield and emissions impact of alternative nutrient management practices or N application rate reductions relative to some agronomic optimum implied by process models
- In reality, optimal application rates and opportunity costs of nutrient management strategies vary considerably across space, time, and cropping systems.
- Regional aggregation of average yield and cost impacts of different practices using models like COMET-FARM to support economic modeling of mitigation pathways may result in overestimating mitigation potential of nutrient management
- Models are only as reliable as the data used to calibrate them – data gaps in the nutrient management domain will continue to be a constraint on decision support.
- In addition to improved physical estimates of the yield and emissions impacts of alternative nutrient management strategies, improved information is needed on behavioral factors, including risk preferences, and how these factors could influence adoption rates.
- A new generation of decision support tools is needed that reflects market and environmental uncertainty, along with behavioral factors that may limit – such tools can improve cost estimates and incentive design choices.

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